

Trace determination of nickel and cadmium(II) amperometrically using 4-*p*-tolyl thiosemicarbazide

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Trace amount of Cd^{II} and Ni^{II} have been estimated quantitatively with 4-*p*-tolyl thiosemicarbazide (4-PTTSC) using amperometric titration technique. The titrations have been performed at pH 6.0 ± 0.02, μ = 0.1 M at RT. The ratio of metal/4-PTTSC is found to be 1 : 2 with L shaped curve. Reverse L shaped curve may be obtained on interchanging the position of 4-PTTSC and metal ion.

A survey of literature reveals that the solid metal complexes of thiosemicarbazide and 4-substituted thiosemicarbazide have been synthesized and studied¹. Analytical data, magnetic moment and spectral data have been explored to elucidate the structure of complexes. Dave *et al.*² introduced various titrimetric methods for the determination of small amount of rare metals. In our earlier work we have reported the use of 4-aryl thiosemicarbazides as an amperometric reagent for determination of Cu^{II} and Zn^{II}³. The present paper deals with the applicability of 4-*p*-tolyl thiosemicarbazide as an amperometric titrant for estimation of small amount of Ni^{II} and Cd^{II}.

Results and discussion

4-PTTSC gives a single oxidation wave in 40% alcohol Britton-Robinson buffer at pH 4.0–11.0. The diffusion current is proportional to the concentration of 4-PTTSC in the observed range, i.e. 1.0 × 10⁻⁴ to 5.0 × 10⁻⁴ M. Sets of the solution containing different but known amount of metal ions, 1 ml 0.001% gelatin in 40% alcoholic BR buffer at μ = 0.1 M (KCl) were prepared. Titrations were performed at the plateau potential of -1.3 V and -0.9 V vs SCE for Ni^{II} and Cd^{II} respectively, at pH 6.20 and 6.00 ± 0.02 with fresh ethanolic solution of the reagent. The solution was deaerated with nitrogen for five minutes prior to the addition of titrant from the micro burette. The fresh solution of 4-PTTSC was added dropwise from a semi micro burette. The current readings were corrected for volume changes. On plotting [(V + v)/V] × i against titrant volume, L shaped curve was obtained in both the cases. The end point indicates metal : 4-PTTSC ratio of 1 : 2.

Ultra micro and micro quantities of Ni^{II} and Cd^{II} have been determined by the recommended procedure using 4-*p*-tolyl thiosemicarbazide. The minimum amount of each of the titled metals evaluated at optimum concentration range is 0.31 mg with practical error less than ±0.09%. The accuracy of the method was tested by analysing said metals with different amount of 4-PTTSC (Table 1). The precision and accuracy of the method was ascertained by carrying out statistical analysis of the results from a series of study, which show excellent accuracy and reproducibility.

Table 1. Amperometric determination of Cd^{II} and Ni^{II} with 4-*p*-tolyl thiosemicarbazide

For amount of Cd ^{II} (mg) :			
Sl. no.	Taken	Found	Error %
1.	0.3917	0.3885	-0.81
2.	0.4671	0.4639	-0.68
3.	0.5595	0.5624	+0.51
4.	0.7299	0.7329	+0.41
5.	0.9994	1.0015	+0.21
6.	1.1190	1.1155	-0.31
7.	1.4547	1.4578	+0.21
For amount of Ni ^{II} (mg) :			
1.	0.2478	0.2499	+0.84
2.	0.3018	0.3049	-0.61
3.	0.5192	0.5164	-0.53
4.	0.6726	0.6761	+0.52
5.	0.9145	0.9183	+0.41
6.	1.0148	1.0109	+0.38
7.	1.1852	1.1816	+0.30

Plateau potential : Cd = -0.09; Ni = -1.4 V vs SCE, supporting electrolyte : Cd = Ni = BR buffer, ionic strength : Cd = Ni = 0.1 M, pH : Cd = Ni = 6.00 ± 0.02, temp. : Cd = Ni = 27 ± 1°, standard deviation : Cd = ±0.004; Ni = ±0.002, coefficient of variation : Cd = 1.05; Ni = 1.05.

Diverse ion effect :

In the determination of Ni^{II} :

(a) Li⁺, Na⁺, K⁺, Al³⁺ and Mg²⁺ did not hamper the titration procedure up to 70 fold excess over Ni^{II} concentration. (b) Cl⁻, SO₄²⁻, NO₃⁻, CH₃COO⁻ did not interfere at all and (c) Co²⁺, Cd²⁺, Mn²⁺ etc. interfered the titration procedure.

In the determination of Cd^{II} :

(a) Li⁺, Na⁺, K⁺, Ca²⁺ and Mg²⁺ did not hampered the titration procedure up to 80 fold excess over Cd^{II} concentration. (b) Cl⁻, NO₃⁻, SO₄²⁻ and CH₃COO⁻ did not interfere at all and (c) Ni²⁺, Co²⁺, Pb²⁺ interfered the amperometric titration of Cd^{II} if present in small amount.

Experimental

All the chemicals used were of extra pure grade. Cd and Ni solutions were prepared by dissolving the respective soluble salts in distilled water and standardized⁴. 4-*p*-Tolyl thiosemicarbazide abbreviated as 4-PTTSC is synthesized as reported in the literature⁵. The product was routinely checked for purity by TLC on silica gel. Fresh solution of 4-PTTSC was prepared in absolute ethanol whenever required. Polarographic recordings were performed on Elico CL-90 pulse polarograph, which was coupled with an x-y polarocord LR-108. The electrochemical cell used had a provision for inserting the dropping mercury electrode as a working electrode, a saturated calomel electrode as a reference electrode and platinum wire electrode as an auxiliary electrode, a bubbler for deaerating the solution and for passing nitrogen gas.

For amperometric titrations⁶ of the metals, a manually operated polarograph with Tinsley potentiometer and multi-flex galvanometer (Sens. = 8.10×10^{-9} amp./div.) was used. Dropping mercury electrode (d.m.e.) with capillary characteristics of $m^{2/3} t^{1/6} = 2.214 \text{ mg}^{1/2}$ at 40 cm effective height

of mercury column was used as an indicator electrode. A calomel electrode was used as a reference electrode. The pH of the test solutions was measured on an Elico LI-120 digital pH meter and adjusted to the required value with the help of buffers. Throughout the course of studies double-distilled mercury was used. Each of the test solution was deaerated by bubbling purified nitrogen gas before titration for five minutes. All titrations were performed at RT. Stock solution of titled metals (0.01 M) was prepared by direct weighing the requisite chemicals.

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